

CONTINUATION OF THE SOLUTION OF MOISIL-THEODORESCO'S
SYSTEM OF EQUATIONS

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Annotation. Solvability conditions and continuation formulas of boundary value problem for the inhomogeneous Cauchy - Riemann equation are obtained. In three dimensional space the similar results for the system of equations of Moisil-Theodoresko are established.

Keywords. continuation; Cauchy-Riemann equation; Dirichlet problem; Sokhotskii - Plemelj formula; harmonic polynomials.

In three-dimensional Euclidean space R^3 , the analogue of the Cauchy-Riemann system is the system of Moisil-Theodoresco (MT)

$$D\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_3}\right)q(x) = 0, \tag{1}$$

where the matrix differential operator D is given by

$$D(X) = D(X_1, X_2, X_3) = \left\| \begin{array}{cccc} 0 & X_1 & X_2 & X_3 \\ X_1 & 0 & -X_3 & X_2 \\ X_2 & X_3 & 0 & -X_1 \\ X_3 & -X_2 & X_1 & 0 \end{array} \right\|, \tag{2}$$

$$X_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}, i = 1, 2, 3, q = (q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4), x = (x_1, x_2, x_3).$$

This is an elliptic system of the first order with respect to an unknown vector q .

Let the domain D_i in space R^3 is bounded by a piecewise smooth closed surface S and D_e – is an external unbounded domain, that is $D_e = R^3 \setminus \bar{D}_i$. Denote the matrix differential operator by $N(x, y)$

$$N(x, y) = -D^* \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_3} \right) \frac{1}{|x - y|} D \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_3} \right),$$

where

$$D^*(X_1, X_2, X_3)$$

is a matrix

$$D^*(X) = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & X_1 & X_2 & X_3 \\ X_1 & 0 & X_3 & -X_2 \\ X_2 & -X_3 & 0 & X_1 \\ X_3 & X_2 & -X_1 & 0 \end{vmatrix},$$

and $|x - y|$ is a distance between the points x and y of the space R^3 . For points $y \in S$ consider the matrix

$$M(x, y) = -D^* \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_3} \right) \frac{1}{|x - y|} D(\nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3)$$

where $\nu = (\nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3)$ is the unit vector of the external normal (i.e., the normal directed to D_e) to the surface S at the point $y \in S$. If $q(x)$ is continuous in $\bar{D}_i$, with its first-order derivatives, then the following analogue of the Borel-Pompei formula holds [1]:

$$\frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S M(x, y) q(y) dS_y - \frac{1}{4\pi} \iiint_{D_i} N(x, y) q(y) d\tau_y = \begin{cases} q(x), & x \in D_i, \\ 0, & x \in D_e. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

When $\gamma(y) = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \gamma_4)$ – is a continuous vector-function given on S , the expression

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S M(x, y) \gamma(y) dS_y \quad (4)$$

is called an integral of Cauchy type for the MT system. The Cauchy-type integral $p(x)$ represented by formula (4) at each point $x \notin S$ is a solution of the MT system. The values of this integral in the domains D_i and D_e is denoted by $p^i(x)$ and $p^e(x)$, respectively.

Consider the Dirichlet problem for inhomogeneous system MT

$$D\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_3}\right)q(x) = f(x), \quad x \in D_i, \quad (5)$$

$$q(y) = \gamma(y), \quad y \in S. \quad (6)$$

This problem is incorrect, as in the case of the Cauchy-Riemann inhomogeneous equation. It is not solvable for any boundary data. We are interested in the solvability conditions for problem (5), (6). First, consider the case of a homogeneous MT system, i.e. $f(x) \equiv 0$. The existence of a solution of the Dirichlet problem for homogeneous MT system is closely related to the condition for the inversion of the integral of Cauchy type (4) to the Cauchy integral. Assume that a vector- function $\gamma(y)$ on a surface S satisfies the Hölder condition. The conversion condition for an integral of Cauchy type (4) to the Cauchy integral is the relationship

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow y} p^i(x) = \gamma(y), \quad y \in S, \quad x \in D_i. \quad (7)$$

THEOREM 1. Let S – homomorphic to the sphere closed Lyapunov surface separating R^3 in two domains D_i and D_e ; $\gamma(y)$ – the vector function given on S and satisfies to the Gelder condition. In order to the Cauchy type integral (4) transforms into Cauchy integral, it is necessary and sufficient that $p^e(x) \equiv 0$ in the domain D_e .

Proof. Necessity. On the basis of the analogue of the Sokhotsky-Plemel formula for an integral of Cauchy type (4), at each fixed point $x_0 \in S$, the equality is satisfied

$$p^i(x^0) - p^e(x^0) = \gamma(x^0). \quad (8)$$

If conditions (7) are satisfied, from (8) follows

$$p^e(x^0) = 0, \quad x^0 \in S. \quad (9)$$

Due to the uniqueness of the solution of the Dirichlet problem, it follows from (9) that $p^e(x) \equiv 0$ in the domain D_e .

SUFFICIENCY. Let the vector-function γ satisfy the condition $p^e(x) \equiv 0$. Then from (8) it follows that $p^i(x^0) = \gamma(x^0)$, $x^0 \in S$.

THEOREM 2. Let the conditions of the theorem are fulfilled. In order to the Cauchy type integral for the system (MT) transforms into Cauchy integral, it is necessary and sufficient that for all harmonic polynomials $H(x)$ of variables x^1, x^2, x^3 fulfill the equality

$$\iint_S D^* \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_3} \right) H(y) D(v_1, v_2, v_3) \gamma(y) dS_y = 0.$$

PROOF. For the function $p^e(x)$ we have the presentation

$$p^e(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S M(x, y) \gamma(y) dS_y, \quad x \in D_e$$

with theorem 1, we obtain

$$\iint_S D^* \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y_3} \right) \frac{1}{|x-y|} D(v_1, v_2, v_3) \gamma(y) dS_y = 0, \quad x \in D_e. \quad (10)$$

Passing to spherical coordinates $x = (\rho, \theta, \varphi)$, $y = (\rho', \theta', \varphi')$ for sufficiently large ρ in (10), we substitute the fundamental solution of the Laplace equation by its expansion into a uniformly convergent series in spherical functions [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{|x-y|} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{P_n(\cos \theta)}{\rho^{n+1}} H_n^{(0)}(\rho', \theta', \varphi') + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(n-k)! P_n^{(k)}(\cos \theta)}{(n+k)! \rho^{n+1}} \times \\ &\times \left[\cos k\varphi H_n^{(k)}(\rho', \theta', \varphi') + \sin k\varphi H_n^{(-k)}(\rho', \theta', \varphi') \right] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $P_n(\cos \theta)$ is the Legendre polynomial of n power on $\cos \theta$, $P_n^{(k)}(\cos \theta)$ - are associated Legendre functions of n power and k ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) order. Functions

$$\begin{aligned} H_n^{(0)}(\rho', \theta', \varphi') &= (\rho')^n P_n(\cos \theta'), \\ H_n^{(k)}(\rho', \theta', \varphi') &= (\rho')^n P_n^{(k)}(\cos \theta') \cos k\varphi', \end{aligned}$$

$$H_n^{(-k)}(\rho', \theta', \varphi') = (\rho')^n P_n^{(k)}(\cos \theta') \sin k\varphi',$$

form a basis for the lineal of harmonic polynomials in variables y^1, y^2, y^3 .

Substituting in the equality (10) instead of $\frac{1}{r}$ by its decomposition (11), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{P_n(\cos \vartheta)}{\rho^{n+1}} \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H_{(n)}^{(0)}(\rho', \vartheta', \varphi') D(v) \gamma(y) dS_y + \\ & + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(n-k)! P_n(\cos \vartheta)}{(n+k)! \rho^{n+1}} [\cos k\varphi' \times \\ & \times \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H_n^{(k)}(\rho', \vartheta', \varphi') D(v) \gamma(y) dS_y + \\ & + \sin k\varphi' \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H_n^{(-k)}(\rho', \vartheta', \varphi') D(v) \gamma(y) dS_y] = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

As functions $\left\{ \frac{1}{\rho^{n+1}} P_n^{(k)}(\cos \theta') \Big|_{\sin k\varphi}^{\cos k\varphi} \right\}$ form a basis, from (12), we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H_m^{(0)}(\rho', \vartheta', \varphi') D(v) \gamma(y) ds_y = 0, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \\ & \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H_m^{(k)}(\rho', \vartheta', \varphi') D(v) \gamma(y) ds_y = 0, \\ & \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H_m^{(-k)}(\rho', \vartheta', \varphi') D(v) \gamma(y) ds_y = 0, \quad k, m = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{13}$$

As the systems of functions $H_m^{(0)}, H_m^{(k)}, H_m^{(-k)}$ form a basis in the linear space of harmonic polynomials, then for any harmonic polynomial $H(y)$ there is an expansion

$$H(y) = \sum_{m=0}^n \alpha_m^0 H_m^0(y) + \sum_{m=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \alpha_m^k H_m^k(y) + \sum_{m=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \beta_m^k H_m^k(y) \tag{14}$$

where $\alpha_m^{(k)}, \beta_m^{(k)}$ – are constant values. Multiplying equalities (13) by $\alpha_m^{(k)}, \beta_m^{(k)}$, respectively, and summing, we get

$$\iint_S D^*(\partial y) H(y) D(v) \gamma(y) dS_y = 0. \tag{15}$$

SUFFICIENCY. Let the vector-function $\gamma(y)$ satisfy condition (15). Then conditions (13) are also satisfied. From (12) and (11) follows the satisfaction of condition (10). Then from $p^e(x) \equiv 0$ and theorem 1 the Cauchy type integral (4) is converted to the Cauchy integral. The theorem is proved.

The conditions of conversion of the Green type integral to the Green integral are considered for harmonic functions [2].

Consider the Dirichlet problem for the inhomogeneous MT system, that is, problem (5), (6).

THEOREM 3. Let S be a homeomorphic sphere of the closed Lyapunov surface, $f(y)$ – is a vector-function given on S satisfying the Hölder condition. The Dirichlet problem (5), (6) is solvable if and only if the following conditions are satisfied

$$\frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S M(x, y) \gamma(y) dS_y - \frac{1}{2\pi} \iiint_{D_i} N(x, y) f(y) d\tau_y = 0, \quad x \in D_e. \quad (16)$$

If this condition is satisfied, then the unique solution is given by the formula

$$q(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S M(x, y) \gamma(y) dS_y - \frac{1}{2\pi} \iiint_{D_i} N(x, y) f(y) d\tau_y, \quad x \in D_i. \quad (17)$$

The proof of this theorem is carried out by formula (3) in a manner similar to the proof of Theorem 1, since the volume integral on the right-hand side of (17), if viewed throughout the space, is a continuous function. In the domain D_i this integral satisfies the inhomogeneous MT system (5), and in the domain D_e – the inhomogeneous MT system MT (3).

THEOREM 4. Let the conditions of the theorem 3 are fulfilled. In order to the Dirichlet problem (5), (6) is solvable, it is necessary and sufficient, that for all harmonic polynomials $H(x)$ of variables x^1, x^2, x^3 fulfill the equality

$$\frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S D^*(\partial y) H(y) D(v) \gamma(y) dS_y + \frac{1}{2\pi} \iiint_{D_i} D^*(\partial y) H(y) D(v) f(y) dS_y = 0. \quad (18)$$

If this condition is satisfied, then the unique solution is given by formula (17).

The proof of this theorem is similar to the proof of Theorem 2, using Theorem 3.

Consider the problem of continuation of the solution of the MT system from a part of the boundary. Let $D = B_R$ be a ball in R^3 with a center at the origin, and S – a smooth closed surface dividing it into two connected components D^+ and D^- , so that the domain D^+ contains zero. Our aim is to obtain a formula of continuation for the solution of the MT system in the domain D^- from its boundary values on the surface S . For this purpose, the expansion of the fundamental solution of the Laplace equation in a series of homogeneous harmonic polynomials is used. At $x \in D^-, y \in \partial D^- \setminus S$ the fundamental solution of the Laplace equation $r^{-1} = |x - y|^{-1}$ can be expanded in a series (27):

$$\frac{1}{r} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{P_n(\cos \mathcal{G}')}{(\rho')^{n+1}} H_{(n)}^{(0)}(\rho, \mathcal{G}, \varphi) + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(n-k)! P_n(\cos \mathcal{G}')}{(n+k)! (\rho')^{n+1}} [\cos k\varphi' \times \times H_n^{(k)}(\rho, \mathcal{G}, \varphi) + \sin k\varphi' H_n^{(-k)}(\rho, \mathcal{G}, \varphi)]. \quad (19)$$

If the point x belongs to a compact subset of domain D^- , then the series (19) converges uniformly with respect to y on the set $\partial D^- \setminus S$ with its derivatives of any order. For $m = 1, 2, \dots$ the function $G_m(x, y)$ is denoted by

$$G_m(x, y) = \frac{1}{r} - \sum_{n=0}^m \frac{P_n(\cos \mathcal{G}')}{(\rho')^{n+1}} H_{(n)}^{(0)}(\rho, \mathcal{G}, \varphi) - 2 \sum_{n=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(n-k)! P_n(\cos \mathcal{G}')}{(n+k)! (\rho')^{n+1}} [\cos k\varphi' \times \times H_n^{(k)}(\rho, \mathcal{G}, \varphi) + \sin k\varphi' H_n^{(-k)}(\rho, \mathcal{G}, \varphi)] = \frac{1}{r} - g_m(x, y).$$

LEMMA. The function $G_m(x, y)$ is harmonic in x and y everywhere except the sets $\{x = y\}$ u $\{y \neq 0\}$.

The proof follows from the properties of the function r^{-1} and of the polynomials $H_n^{(k)}$.

THEOREM 5. For a vector function $q(x)$ satisfying in the domain D^- the homogeneous MT system that is continuous in a closed domain $\bar{D}^-$, the following formula is true

$$q(x) = -\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S D^*(\partial y) G_m(x, y) D(\nu) q(y) dS_y, \quad x \in D^-, \quad (20)$$

where the limit is attained uniformly on each compact set $K \subset D^-$.

PROOF. Under the hypotheses of the theorem, from (3) for the function $q(x)$ follows the validity of formula

$$q(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_{\partial D^-} M(x, y) q(y) dS_y, \quad x \in D^-. \quad (21)$$

Since the function $g_m(x, y)$ is harmonic on y in domain D^- and continuous in the closed domain $\bar{D}^-$, the equality is held

$$\frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_{\partial D^-} D^*(\partial y) g_m(x, y) D(\nu) q(y) dS_y = 0, \quad x \in D^-. \quad (22)$$

From (21) and (22) we get

$$q(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_{\partial D^-} D^*(\partial y) G_m(x, y) D(\nu) q(y) dS_y, \quad x \in D^-.$$

Hence, passing to the limit at $m \rightarrow \infty$, on the basis of (19) we obtain (20).

Remark 1. The Dirichlet problem for the inhomogeneous polyanalytic equation in other way was considered in [3], [4].

Remark 2. The Fok–Kuni theorem for the generalized analytic functions was obtained in [5].

Remark 3. The Fock-Cuni theorem for polyanalytic functions was obtained in [6].

References

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